

Experimental Replication of a Reported pH-Sensitive Biopolymer Packaging Film under Resource-Limited Laboratory Conditions

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ABSTRACT

Intelligent food packaging films based on natural pH-sensitive dyes have attracted attention for monitoring food spoilage. However, reproducibility under limited laboratory resources remains insufficiently explored in undergraduate laboratory environments. In this work, a reported chitosan/poly(vinyl alcohol)/anthocyanin (CS/PVA/ATH) film preparation protocol was replicated with controlled proportional reduction of reagents and modified casting conditions. All reagents were reduced to 50% of reported quantities while preserving compositional ratios, and films were cast in smaller Petri dishes and dried for shorter durations (6–8 h vs. 72 h). The obtained films successfully formed continuous layers, showed swelling behavior in aqueous media, and exhibited rapid colorimetric response (<30 s) across acidic to basic conditions. Observed color transitions were consistent with literature reports (red → purple → blue-green → yellow-green). Despite shortened drying time and reduced volume, functional performance remained comparable to the original method. The study demonstrates robustness of anthocyaninbased intelligent packaging films and confirms feasibility of fabrication in resourceconstrained laboratory settings.

1. INTRODUCTION

Food spoilage results in chemical changes that alter pH due to microbial metabolism and protein degradation. Intelligent packaging materials capable of indicating pH variation provide a lowcost visual method for freshness monitoring. Natural pigments such as anthocyanins extracted from red cabbage exhibit strong colorimetric response to pH and have been widely incorporated into biodegradable polymer matrices.

Chitosan and poly(vinyl alcohol) are commonly used biopolymers due to film-forming ability, mechanical stability, and biocompatibility. Vo et al. (2019) demonstrated successful fabrication of CS/PVA/anthocyanin films crosslinked using sodium tripolyphosphate (STPP) for pHindicative food packaging.

While such studies demonstrate functionality, replication feasibility in teaching laboratories with limited reagents, restricted equipment time, and smaller casting setups remains underreported. This work aims to reproduce the reported film using proportionally reduced materials and modified drying conditions to evaluate robustness of the fabrication protocol.

This study does not aim to introduce a novel material but to evaluate reproducibility under constrained laboratory conditions.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Fresh red cabbage (*Brassica oleracea*) was used as the source of anthocyanin pigment. Poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA, Mw 89,000–98,000), chitosan (75–85% deacetylated), sodium tripolyphosphate (STPP), glacial acetic acid, hydrochloric acid (37%), sodium hydroxide, ethanol (analytical grade), and deionized water were used for film fabrication. All reagents were of laboratory grade and used without further purification.

The experimental design followed the protocol reported by Vo et al. (2019), with proportional reduction of reagents and modified casting conditions due to laboratory resource limitations.

2.2 Reference Protocol (Vo et al., 2019)

The reported method utilized the following quantities:

- Red cabbage: 150 g
- Ethanol: 150 mL
- Deionized water: 150 mL
- HCl: 3 mL
- PVA: 1 g dissolved in 100 mL water
- Chitosan: 2 g dissolved in 200 mL of 1% acetic acid
- STPP: 0.1 g dissolved in 100 mL water

Films were cast by pouring 50 mL hydrogel into 120 mm Petri dishes and dried at 45 °C for 72 h.

2.3 Modified Experimental Protocol (This Study)

To evaluate feasibility under resource-limited laboratory conditions, all reagents were reduced to 50% of reported quantities while maintaining identical compositional ratios.

2.3.1 Anthocyanin Extraction

75 g of red cabbage was chopped into small pieces and transferred into a beaker. A solvent mixture consisting of 75 mL ethanol, 75 mL deionized water, and 1.5 mL concentrated HCl was added. The mixture was sonicated in an ultrasonic bath for 60 minutes at room temperature. The extract was filtered to remove solid residues and stored in a dark container until use.

Figure 1. Extraction of anthocyanin pigment from red cabbage using ethanol–water–HCl solvent system.

2.3.2 Preparation of Polymer Solutions

PVA Solution (1%)

0.5 g of PVA was dissolved in 50 mL deionized water at approximately 70 °C with continuous stirring until a clear solution formed. The solution was cooled to room temperature.

Chitosan Solution (1%)

1 g chitosan was dissolved in 100 mL of 1% acetic acid solution (prepared using glacial acetic acid in water) and stirred for 24 hours at room temperature until uniform dispersion was obtained.

STPP Solution (0.1%)

0.05 g STPP was dissolved in 50 mL deionized water.

The prepared solutions are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Preparation of polymer solutions used for film fabrication: (a) PVA solution; (b) STPP crosslinker solution; (c) chitosan solution after 24 h stirring.

2.3.3 Preparation of Film-Forming Hydrogel

The PVA and chitosan solutions were mixed in a 35:65 (v/v) ratio.

Anthocyanin extract corresponding to 25% of the final volume was added and stirred for 30 minutes.

Subsequently, STPP solution equivalent to 6% of the mixture volume was added dropwise under continuous stirring to promote crosslinking.

The pH of the hydrogel was adjusted to approximately 6 using 1 M NaOH.

2.3.4 Film Casting and Drying

Due to limited Petri dish size, 17 mL of hydrogel was poured into 90 mm diameter Petri dishes instead of 50 mL into 120 mm dishes used in the reference protocol..

The casting volumes were 17 mL, 17 mL, and 16 mL (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Casting of CS/PVA/ATH hydrogel into Petri dishes before drying

Films were dried in a laboratory oven at 45 °C (Figure 4). Because of restricted oven availability, drying time was limited to 8 hours; however, complete solvent evaporation occurred within approximately 6 hours. The shorter drying duration was attributed to reduced film thickness and lower total solvent content.

After drying, the films formed continuous transparent layers and adhered strongly to the Petri dish surface. Careful peeling was required to prevent tearing.

Figure 4. Drying of films at 45 °C inside laboratory oven.

After drying, films were carefully peeled and stored at room temperature prior to testing.

2.4 pH Sensitivity Testing

Film samples were exposed to aqueous solutions of varying pH conditions. Color change was visually recorded and response time was noted. Swelling behavior in liquid media was also qualitatively observed.

Figure 5. Prepared buffer solutions used for evaluation of pH sensitivity.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Film Formation

The prepared hydrogel formed a continuous film after drying. The film adhered strongly to the casting surface and required careful peeling. The film exhibited flexibility but remained delicate during handling.

3.2 pH Response

The film displayed rapid color change (<30 s) across pH conditions:

Acidic → pink/red

Neutral → purple

Basic → green/yellow-green

The observed color transition pattern was consistent with anthocyanin structural transformation across pH environments

Figure 6. Colorimetric response of fabricated film under different pH conditions.

3.3 Swelling Behavior

When exposed to aqueous solutions, the film showed swelling without dissolution, indicating crosslinked polymer network formation.

Figure 7. Swelling behavior of the crosslinked film in aqueous media.

3.4 Effect of Reduced Drying Time

Complete drying occurred within 6 hours due to reduced thickness and casting volume, significantly shorter than previously reported 72 hours.

4. DISCUSSION

The successful formation of a functional pH-indicative film under reduced material quantities demonstrates robustness of the CS/PVA/ATH system. Comparable colorimetric response indicates that functional performance depends more on compositional ratios than absolute quantities.

Shortened drying time did not compromise functionality, suggesting scalability potential in industrial or educational environments where extended drying is impractical. Adhesion to the Petri dish indicates strong polymer interaction and effective crosslinking.

The study supports feasibility of intelligent packaging film fabrication in resource-limited teaching laboratories. Due to qualitative visual evaluation, the sensitivity threshold and detection accuracy could not be quantified.

5. LIMITATIONS

- No mechanical tensile strength measurement
 - No real food spoilage testing
 - Qualitative color evaluation only
 - Limited environmental control during drying
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6. CONCLUSION

A previously reported intelligent food packaging film was successfully replicated using halfscale reagents and significantly shorter drying duration. The fabricated film retained pH sensitivity and swelling characteristics, confirming reproducibility and adaptability of the fabrication process. This demonstrates the practicality of implementing biosensor-based packaging experiments in constrained laboratory settings.

7. REFERENCE

Vo, T.-V., Dang, T.-H., & Chen, B.-H. (2019). Synthesis of intelligent pH-indicative films from chitosan/poly(vinyl alcohol)/anthocyanin extracted from red cabbage. *Polymers*, 11(7), 1088. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym11071088>

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